

Effect of dislocation and honeycomb height on compression performance of tandem honeycomb

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Flatwise compression specimen

Experimental results

Parametric simulations

Parametric simulations

Conclusion

1. The collapse stress of tandem honeycomb can be increased by more than 5% compared to single honeycomb. The desired functional layer (such as wave absorbing micro-structure layer) can be added between the honeycomb layers.
2. Dislocation type of corner align like CWC hardly affected in same height double layer, but the difference was greater in honeycomb height, the collapse stress increase caused by the dislocation was more significant.
3. In the case where the height of the core was determined, increasing the layer number of the tandem honeycombs could improve the compression resistance of the core.
4. For double-layer tandem honeycombs, the inconsistent height of the single honeycomb will reduce the compression resistance of the core, and the difference in core height was greater, the performance degradation was more obvious.